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THE EFFECTIVENESS OF NEW PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN THE TEACHING OF PHYSICS

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ABSTRACT

The article notes that physics is a science that teaches phenomena and events in nature and their laws. It has been studied that man, as a part of nature, is directly connected with it, to know the secrets of natural phenomena, to determine their laws, and to improve the living conditions of man.

Physics is the study of events and phenomena in nature and their laws. Man, too, is a part of nature, in direct contact with it. It is carried out in order to know the secrets of natural phenomena, to determine their laws, mainly to improve the living conditions of man. Otherwise, it would have been possible to radically change nature using the achievements of physics. In particular, we would take the sun out or sink at any time, and send rain when needed, turning summer into winter and autumn into summer. In fact, this is not the case, nor can it be. That is why we need to get used to studying the phenomena that occur in nature and using them to preserve the natural resources necessary for human existence, to learn how to use them effectively.

Sandwich technology of education. This technology is related to the economic issue of education. Economists from all over the world say that the contribution of funds allocated to education is low. It is said that the costs incurred in the traditional system of education are in most cases not self-justifying. Therefore, in the recent financial controversy, government spending is declining. This

requires finding new forms of funding the educational process. Its light and easy type is to organize students to get paid education. However, not all parents of those who claim to study have the opportunity to pay for education at all times. In this case, ways were found to suspend the payment of tuition fees as much as possible, and to resume training when the time comes. This technology of teaching is called sandwich technology. Such technology is often aimed at gaining money by paying for it at any time. Parking technology of training. This technology involves teaching students of different ages with the same interests in a special studio. Curricula and programs are selected without state approval, depending on the conditions of the institution and the interests of students. Students who choose the studio will study in groups and individually. Such technology is similar to subject circles in layered teaching. Cyclic or subject technology of teaching. At the beginning of the twentieth century, Russia began the process of transition from traditional course education to subject education. This was often the case with higher education institutions. At present, all higher

education institutions teach several related and unrelated subjects on the same day. In the course, students will be introduced to new material. In most cases, the teacher tells the students the information in the form of ready-made knowledge, but the content of the material is not fully analyzed, as a result its meaning is not revealed. As such a process is repeated throughout the day, this skill becomes a habit and is accepted as an important sign of training. Students who learn little by little in different subjects every day do not even know exactly what they are reading in a day. Because each subject is taught by different teachers, their teaching methods are also different. In addition, the requirements for students' learning activities also differ, and their knowledge is tested in different ways and evaluated by different criteria. As a result, their general teaching methods are not well formed. Contextual technology of teaching. Context is a Latin word that means a strong connection or connection. The meaning of contextual technology of teaching is to teach by linking the learning material with real-life examples, relevant specializations or people's professions. In other words, subject knowledge requires a direct link to social conditions and factors. So, there is a great opportunity to teach physics in a contextual way. It covers all types of technology, transport, communication, technical media, information technology, internet and satellite communication, agriculture, consumer services, energy and others, which develop all aspects of scientific and technological development. This will help prepare students for life and work as well as help them become better professionals in the future.

In conclusion, the teacher organizes a comprehensive discussion, summarizes the answers of students, directs their research

activities in the desired direction, shows them the mistakes they made in creating a methodological situation, and monitors the implementation of the work. During the course of the game, his supervisor must act as a referee without fully telling the students that the problem will be solved. At the end, he should look at the state of the game, identify the activities of the participants, focus on the right solutions, highlight their effective option, and offer students additional literature on the problem discussed in the workshop.

ROLL GAME METHOD- is a method used by learners to demonstrate various life situations. The difference between role-playing games and business games is that there is no evaluation. At the same time, while role-playing learners are content to play roles in a scenario developed by the educator, role-play learners are free to decide for themselves what tasks to perform in a given situation. In a role-playing game, the participants work together to solve a problem, such as a business game. Role-playing games develop interpersonal skills in learners. The role-playing educator must have prior knowledge of the learners. Because in playing roles, the individual character and behavior of each learner plays an important role. The topics chosen should be appropriate to the level of mastery of the learners. Role-playing games help to motivate learners in the learning process. The structure of the role-playing method is given below. The purpose and tasks of the game are explained Roles are distributed. Roles are played. The final conclusion is reached.

The structure of the role-playing method The stages of the role-playing method are as follows: 1. The teacher determines the goals and results of the game on the topic and develops a role-playing scenario. 2. The goals and objectives of the game are explained. 3.

Allocates roles based on the purpose of the game. 4. Learners play their roles. Other learners follow them. 5. At the end of the game, learners are given the opportunity to

explain how they can play the role they played again. Learners who are observers will give their final feedback and summarize the game

References:

1. Teoreticheskie osnovy soderjaniya obshego srednego obrazovaniya. - M .: Pedagogika, 1983 61. Usova A.V.
2. Formirovanie u shkolnikov nauchnyx ponyatij v protsesse obucheniya. - M .: Pedagogika, 1986 62. Usova A.V.
3. Theory and methods of teaching physics.- St. Petersburg: Medusa, 2002 63. Feynman R. Character of physical laws. - M .: Nauka, 1987 64. Shodiev D.Sh.
4. Myslennyy eksperiment v prepodavanii fizik.- M .: Prosveshchenie, 1987 65. Esaulov A.F. Activation uchebno-poznavatelnoy deyatelnosti students. - M .: Vysshaya shkola, 1982